

ESI-MS Report

University
of Basel

Department of
Chemistry

Sample Information

Acquired by	: System Administrator
Date Acquired	: 10.09.2018 14:26:56
Sample Name	: MEM012
Sample ID	:
Data File	: MEM012.lcd
Method File	: MEM012.lcm
Original Method File	: MEM012.lcm
Report Format File	: DEFAULT.lsr
Tuning File	: Installation_nachUmzug_170831.lct
Processed by	: System Administrator
Date Processed	: 10.09.2018 14:29:10

Method

<<Header>>

Generated	: 08.11.2017 11:41:44
Modified	: 08.11.2017 11:41:44

<<MS Parameter>>

Initial Valve Position	:-
--Segment 1 Event 1--	
Start Time	:0.00 min
End Time	:3.00 min
Acquisition Mode	:Profile
Polarity	:Positive
Event Time	:1.00 sec
Detector Voltage	:+1.15 kV
Start m/z	:100.00
End m/z	:2000.00
Scan Speed	:2143 u/sec
Interface Volt.	:Use the Data in the Tuning File
DL Volt.	:Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	:Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	:Use the Data in the Tuning File
--Segment 1 Event 2--	
Start Time	:0.00 min
End Time	:3.00 min
Acquisition Mode	:Profile
Polarity	:Negative
Event Time	:1.00 sec
Detector Voltage	:+1.05 kV
Start m/z	:100.00
End m/z	:800.00
Scan Speed	:715 u/sec
Interface Volt.	:Use the Data in the Tuning File
DL Volt.	:Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	:Use the Data in the Tuning File
Qarray DC Voltage	:Use the Data in the Tuning File

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan

Line#:1 R.Time:0.000(Scan#:1)
MassPeaks:11
Spectrum Mode:Single 0.000(1) Base Peak:641.10(9081931)
BG Mode:None Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan Zoomed View

Line#:1 R.Time:0.000(Scan#:1)
MassPeaks:11
Spectrum Mode:Single 0.000(1) Base Peak:641.10(9081931)
BG Mode:None Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Positive Full Scan Zoomed View

Line#:1 R.Time:0.000(Scan#:1)
MassPeaks:11
Spectrum Mode:Single 0.000(1) Base Peak:641.10(9081931)
BG Mode:None Segment 1 - Event 1

MS Spectrum Negative mode
Line#:2 R.Time:0.015(Scan#:2)
MassPeaks:3
Spectrum Mode:Single 0.015(2) Base Peak:312.88(353853)
BG Mode:None Segment 1 - Event 2

MS Spectrum Negative mode Zoomed view
Line#:2 R.Time:0.015(Scan#:2)
MassPeaks:3
Spectrum Mode:Single 0.015(2) Base Peak:312.88(353853)
BG Mode:None Segment 1 - Event 2

